

Quest for a Major Power Status: An Overview of the Challenges Facing India's Foreign Policy in the 21st Century

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The Context

Ever since India attained its independence in August 1947 the makers of the foreign policy of the newly sovereign state-led by Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister-were driven by two principal goals: retention of complete autonomy in the pursuit of its foreign policy to safeguard India's national interests and the determination to make a major impact on the course of post world war II international relations defined as it was by the cold war rivalry between the United States led 'western bloc' and the Soviet Union led bloc located primarily in Eastern Europe. This is not to say that the other objectives of India's foreign policy such as decolonisation, disarmament, strong moral and material support for the United Nations and peaceful co-existence in a nuclearised world were any less important. However, it was strongly felt that if the two. primary goals were not met India would not be able to make any effective contribution on the other issues which bedevilled the world at the time. As is well known the fundamental instrument chosen by Jawaharlal Nehru to pursue the basic goals of India's foreign policy, mentioned above, was non-alignment .which was meant to perform the essential functions of ensuring the autonomy of India's foreign policy as well as give it a significant voice in international relations as the heir to a great civilisational heritage. As has been recounted in numerous writings on India's foreign policy during the cold war years although non-alignment substantially served many of the basic goals of India the complexities of its regional environment-especially in relations to China and Pakistan-in the 1950s, 1960s and the 1970s compelled New Delhi to substantially re-orient its foreign policy approach which need not be recounted here. This paper is concerned with the

trajectory of India's foreign policy in the 21st century taking on board the dramatic transformation of the world following the end of the Cold war and its consequent ramifications for India's foreign policy whose contours and character have acquired dimensions hardly imaginable even in the late 1980s. The scope of the subject is so vast that it is not possible to go into the details of the multiple dimensions and not just political and diplomatic-that contribute to the formulations of foreign policies in the 21st century. The paper will attempt to provide a broad overview of the principal challenges that confront Indian foreign policy in the present century. It will begin by briefly delineating the monumental transformation the world scenario underwent following the end of the cold war and the demise of the Soviet Union in the early 1990s. That will set the backdrop of the dramatically changed external milieu which posed fundamental challenges for the formulation of an Indian foreign policy which is anchored in the basic maxim of any sound foreign policy-namely continuity and change. As is well known the foreign policy of any state is a product of interplay of domestic as also of external factors. The paper will therefore examine the domestic challenges that India has faced and continues to face over the last two decades. It will then explore the external challenges India has to deal with in the present century. The discussion will be wrapped up with a concluding section that takes on board the current concerns of India's foreign policy makers and the prospects for the future. The post-cold war world scenario has been extensively covered in the vast literature on foreign policy. The collapse of the Soviet bloc led to the end of the bi polar world order and the emergence of the much talked about uni polar era dominated overwhelmingly by the United States. The Soviet

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collapse has been viewed not only as the final victory of capitalism over socialism but it also signalled the onset of a globalisation which seemed to herald the imposition of a market based era the world over. Along with the emergence of economics and finance capital as powerful factors the world entered a complex era which made it difficult to define the central trends, powers and forces that would seek to determine the course of international relations.

This is the backdrop India's policy makers had to contend with while determining and reorienting New Delhi's foreign policy in this new era. It had to contend with developments such as the emergence of the US as the sole military superpower, the evolution of trading blocs such as the 'North Atlantic Free Trade Agreement, (NAFTA), the emergence of the European Union (EU) and the formation of the Asia Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC). New multilateral trading arrangements were set to be put in place under the auspices of the 'World Trade Organisation' (WTO) in which India has a large stake. Along with such constructive trends destructive trends such as the alarming growth of different forms of terrorism and international network of crime syndicates also manifested themselves. Other features of the present era are severe environmental degradation, an explosion of internal conflicts in many developing countries and the consequent displacement of a large number of people both internally and externally. (Hershe and Seethi: 2009:1-2). India was therefore called upon to deal with a radically different world than the one it was familiar with.

The changes in the world scenario also coincided with a dramatic turn around in the Indian economic and developmental strategy with the initiation of the liberalisation of the economy and the adoption of a Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in the early 1990s. This entailed a substantial reduction in the role of the state in the determination of economic and developmental policies making greater room for the private sector, maintenance of fiscal discipline through reduction of state expenditure on salaries and subsidies. Greater attention also needed to be paid to the social sector by mobilising additional resources. As has already been mentioned the challenges posed by globalisation also had to be met by devising suitable policies to deal with a shrinking world and the new forms of cooperation and conflict and the new sets of alliances and counter-alliances that had emerged in the new setting. While globalisation

brought new opportunities (India's information revolution and its emergence as an IT superpower) it also unleashed intensive competition on the productive units and the workforce in India's industrial and agrarian sectors. India needed to form international coalitions with other developing countries to modify the nature of international trade regimes through collective bargaining. (Hershe and Seethi: 2009:3).

In undertaking the efforts to contend with these challenges in the post-cold war era India's policy makers also had to, as has already been mentioned, combine elements of both continuity and change. It essentially meant in this context pursuit of specific national interests in an overall framework of geopolitical and geo-economic priorities. It also required the ability to respond to the evolving international environment. (Hershe and Seethi: 2009:4).

A review of India's foreign policy over the past two decades reveal the extent to which policy makers in New Delhi have been successful in dovetailing the elements of continuity and change in the conceptualisation, formulation and execution of policies.

There is a general consensus that any analysis of India's foreign policy in the 21st century has to take into account the dramatic transformation in the profile of India in the last two decades. In the late 1980s India had an economy barely one-third the size of Italy's. Today it is the fourth largest economy in the world in terms of purchase power parity and prior to the current slowdown of the Indian economy it had been estimated that in the not too distant future it would also overtake Japan, the third largest economy in the world. It is the 9th largest source of industrial output and 3rd largest pool of technical manpower. It is a modern sophisticated military power with one of the largest armies in the world, a well equipped combat ready air force and a navy which possesses aircraft carriers, nuclear submarines and warships of all classes which make it a dominant force in the Indian Ocean region. The Indo-US civil nuclear agreement in 2006 and the subsequent endorsement and acceptance of the Nuclear Suppliers Group (NSG) of India as a legitimate partner in international nuclear trade has been interpreted by many analysts as the final inclusion of India as a legitimate member of the "nuclear club" which ended New Delhi's status as an international nuclear 'pariah' following its refusal to sign the Nuclear Non-Proliferation

Treaty (NPT) and its nuclear tests in 1974 and 1996. On the strategic front the disintegration of the Soviet Union signalled the end of Moscow's diplomatic, military and economic support during the later part of the cold war era which had enabled to balance New Delhi's vital bilateral relationships especially with the United States, China and Pakistan. India is today a rising power bracketed by many experts with China and poised, again in the opinion of many analysts, on the threshold of great power status. India's policy makers too make no secret of the national desire that the international community should acknowledge its potential to emerge as a great power in the not too distant future.

Principal Goals of Foreign Policy in the 21st Century

It is worth our while to take note of the principal goals of India's foreign policy in the 21st century. As is well known to students of India's foreign policy while this country is not a pacifist it has always eschewed any aggressive designs against other states including its close neighbours. However, in the changed circumstances in the world material might and political influence are means and not ends to pursue interests and foreign policy objectives. According to policy makers in New Delhi the desire to attain great power status is primarily for 'defensive' reasons. It is meant to be a protection against external domination or intimidation. (John D. Ciorciari: 2011). Keeping this context in mind four broad goals for India's foreign policy in the 21st century can be identified. These are: 1. Increasing policy autonomy. 2. Securing the state from internal and external threats. 3. Raising the living standards of the people. 4. Winning diplomatic recognition as a leading nation. (Ciorciari: 2011). Experienced students of India's foreign policy will recognise that these are not new goals-especially the first, third and the fourth goals have been rooted in Indian thinking since the immediate post-independence period.

1. Autonomy

As has already been argued earlier this has remained the most important goal of India's foreign policy since independence. For that matter it has to be the vital objective of any state in today's world. Jawaharlal Nehru had made it clear as early as 1946 that an independent foreign policy free from any great power domination was the fundamental objective of independent India's foreign policy.

(Appadorai and Rajan: 1965: 34-35). Nehru made no bones about the fact that he believed that 'India is today among the four great powers of the world: (the) other three being America, Russia and China'. (Jawaharlal Nehru: 1984 & 1995). However these pronouncements were more rhetorical than realistic as in spite of having a large army and population India simply did not possess the material capabilities or political influence to fit under any reasonable definition of a great power. Since then India has acquired a great deal of military and technological power though it still has a long way to go to catch up with the established military powers of today such as the United States, Russia and China. Foreign policy autonomy still remains a central goal. The recent debate regarding the Indo-US Civil nuclear Agreement can be cited to demonstrate the sensitivity of the autonomy issue as the critics of the deal argued that it would compromise the country's hard earned sovereignty and independence. The memory of nearly 200 years of British rule still remains fresh in the psyche of the nation and any perceived or real encroachment on the country's sovereignty remains anathema to the people and the political establishment.

2. Securing the State

A second reason for India's governing elite to acquire greater national capabilities and influence is to ensure internal and external security. As is well known to all students of India's foreign policy the country is located in a dangerous neighbourhood with two hostile neighbours-China and Pakistan with whom India has fought wars during the last five decades. Its relations with these two countries have remained problematic since independence and the security scenario vis-a-vis Beijing and Islamabad turned so hostile in the 1960s and the early 1970s that India had to turn to the Soviet Union for strategic support to protect and preserve the country's fundamental national interests. The relations with China and Pakistan and India's security entwined therewith remains a cornerstone of New Delhi's current concerns and will be taken up in greater detail in a subsequent section. Besides confronting the external security dynamics India is also beset with internal security concerns. The independent India that emerged in 1947 is a mosaic of ethnic, linguistic, religious and regional diversities. While the country has met with relative success in creating a credible democratic federal framework in defusing pressures from diverse and contending religious/linguistic and cultural groups

the effort, over the years, has become increasingly difficult to achieve the objectives in this regard. With demand for greater autonomy for states to restructure Union-State relations the Indian federation has been under pressure from diverse quarters. The onset of the coalition era and the consequent weakening of federal authority along with increasing ethnic and religious conflicts have considerably eroded the foreign policy capability of the government by sapping its attention and energy in managing these conflicts. India's hostile neighbours do not hesitate to exploit these turmoils. Other domestic constraints that preoccupy the government are narco-terrorism, crime-politics nexus, crisis of governance, erosion of values, rise in corruption and economic disparity regionally and among the people. (N.K. Jha: 2009).

3. Pursuing Economic Development

India has faced the challenge of mass poverty since independence. There is a close lineage between economic development and the ability of a state to pursue an effective foreign policy. It strikes some observers as unusual that India is a state which is approaching great power status while most of its population remains poor. (Ciorciari: 2011:7. These observers think that poverty can act as a significant constraint on military build up and economic liberalisation. For a modern welfare state safeguarding national interests in the pursuit of foreign policy also denotes ensuring the well-being and safeguarding the interests of its people. For a country like India it is vital that its policies are able to strike a balance between its quest for a major power status as well as eradicate mass poverty as it is incongruous for a state to be seen to play a major role in international relations while more than 400 million of its people (according to a 2009 Planning Commission, report) survive on less than \$ 1.25 a day. While there is a general consensus that India should have a major say in global affairs this will be difficult to achieve without eradication of mass poverty.

4. Achieving Status and Respect

Achieving social status and influence in international diplomacy has been a longstanding goal of India's foreign policy dating back to 1947. India's size, its heritage as a hub of a great world civilisation and its anti-imperialist credentials have always been considered by its foreign policy makers, especially Jawaharlal Nehru, to make it eminently worthy of regional leadership as also to a major role on the

world stage. (Stephen P.Cohen:2000). However, the governing elite has always felt that the country has not received the recognition on the international stage it deserves. It has never been a member of any of the groupings of the great powers that have dominated international relations since the end of the second world war. So far it has been denied a place in any of these groupings (such as the permanent membership of the UN Security Council, G8, a leading shareholder of the IMF or World Bank). According to Baldev Raj Nayar and T.V. Paul, India has suffered, as a result of this exclusion, from what they call 'status inconsistency'; (Baldev Raj Nayar and T.V. Paul:2003:1). In spite of their hard work even Indian diplomats have found it hard to earn recognition as representatives of a major power. The situation has however begun to change with India's impressive economic growth and military modernisation over the last two decades.

External Challenges

As has been explained in the first section of this paper India faces a variegated plural and complex world order following the end of the cold war. All states have been confronted with the difficult choice of reorienting and adjusting to the multiple dimensions of the complexities the world presents today which have already been referred to earlier. It is in this context I propose to examine the principal external challenges India faces today. I will concentrate on six of them though this is by no means an exhaustive list as it has already been explained that the scope of the paper is confined to a brief overview which cannot incorporate every aspect of the complexities India faces today in its dealings with the world.

1. Strategic Challenges from Pakistan and China

Pakistan

Forging a stable and normal relationship with Pakistan remains the toughest and the most difficult challenge for India. The history of the long drawn-out antagonism between India and Pakistan has been a familiar story to students of south Asian regional politics and has occupied front page for the best part of the history of the two states since their independence. The bitterness, acrimony and conflict that marked the partition of British India created a permanent divide between the two countries that fought four wars between 1947 and 1999. While India accepted the partition with reluctance and tried to work out a normal

relationship with Pakistan Islamabad projected a conviction that India was not reconciled to the creation of Pakistan and was bent upon its destruction. The Kashmir issue further bedevilled the relationship and Pakistan has consistently followed the stratagem that the internationalisation of the problem will work to its advantage. Hence, it has scuttled all efforts towards a bilateral solution as envisaged in the Simla agreement of 1972. The beginning of an insurgency in Kashmir since 1989 has given Pakistan a handle to harass India by actively patronising the Jihadi groups which primarily operate from the soil of Pakistan. This Pakistani sponsorship of terrorism and insurgency in Kashmir over the past twenty five years has not remained confined to the valley alone and has been extended to the rest of India as well the most telling example of which was the terrorist attack on Mumbai on 26 November 2008 which killed 166 people. The irony of the situation is that terrorism is currently taking a terrible toll on Pakistan as well and the challenge that India faces is to convince Islamabad that taking action against terrorists operating from Pakistan would be beneficial for both the countries. However the three power centres of Pakistan—the government, ISI and the army along with the endemic anti-India stance of the Pakistani army have frustrated all efforts of the government of India to convince Islamabad to rein in the Jihadi groups and take meaningful action against the masterminds of the Mumbai attack. The equation has been made far more complicated by the nuclearization of both countries in 1998. Under the circumstances the recalcitrance of Pakistan to take action against terrorism has made the job of beginning and sustaining a bilateral dialogue between India and Pakistan which seems to be the only way out of the quagmire including a solution to the Kashmir tangle, a difficult proposition.

China

The attainment of independence by India in 1947 and the proclamation of the Peoples republic of China by Mao Tse Tung in 1949 radically transformed the landscape of Asia during the post-Second World war period. Jawaharlal Nehru had high hopes that an emergent Asia could be built on the foundation of a strong Sino-Indian friendship. However, things did not take shape according to Nehru's expectations and, as is well known, the India-China relationship went awry, primarily on the issues of Tibet and the disputed boundary between the two countries which culminated in a

border war in 1962 which India lost badly. For the rest of the twentieth century the two countries experienced anything but normal friendly relationship though the diplomatic relations were never ruptured and the two countries maintained regular exchange of visits at the official and leadership level during the 1980s and the 1990s.

Over the past six decades the world has assessed the progress of China and India in comparative terms—a competition and rivalry not only between two major Asian states but also between two systems—communism and democracy. This is not the place to get into a philosophical debate on the subject. However any impartial assessment would show that China has forged far ahead of India by almost every indicator of human and material advancement though India has scored over China on the issue of democracy and human rights. It however remains a fundamental fact of the early 21st century that China has emerged as the second power centre of the world after the United States which is viewed by many observers as a declining power. There simply has been massive change in the standing of China in the last 25 years. It is now the second largest economy of the world after the United States having overtaken Japan. Its GDP is three times that of India, has the largest car market, is the manufacturing hub of the world and possesses foreign exchange exceeding \$3 trillion.

As already mentioned India too has made considerable advancement on the economic, developmental and military fronts though these have not been as spectacular as that of China. India and China are viewed by the world as the symbol of the 'Rise of Asia' because of the impressive growth rates of these countries, particularly since the beginning of this century, resulting from the policy of economic liberalisation, the advances made by them in the field of education, science and technology, and the decline of the western economies, since the unfolding of the economic crisis that hit the US and Europe; there has been a gradual shift in the global balance of power, with India and China seeking to assume greater role in the shaping and management of the world order which was once the exclusive preserve of the western nations. (Arun Kumar Banerji: 2012:3).

However the simultaneous rise of India and China as pre-eminent Asian powers has pitched them into a sort of unannounced rivalry and competition. The hardliners in India view China as a threat to India's security; they point out that China seeks to contain

India through 'proxies' by arming Pakistan with conventional and nuclear weapons, by weaving a string of pearls around India, its convoluted stance on the status of Jammu and Kashmir. For instance it announced in January 1994 that it favoured a negotiated solution to the Kashmir problem and it was also opposed to any form of independence for the region which seemed to be a message for its long term ally Pakistan. (Partha Pratim Basu: 2009:56). However of late Beijing seems to have adopted an ambivalent stand by resorting to issuing (stapled visas) to residents of Jammu and Kashmir wishing to travel to China. This practice of issuing 'stapled visas' is also applied to the residents of Arunachal Pradesh which China considers to be a part of Tibet and therefore of China itself. The border issue remains unresolved and shows no signs of resolution in the near future despite numerous rounds of negotiations between the two sides over the past two decades. The optimists in India however emphasise the commonality of interests between the two neighbours in terms of combating the growing fundamentalist and terrorist menace, cooperation in countering climate change and environmental degradation, dealing with resource and especially energy scarcity, maintaining access to capital and markets and evolving joint strategies to derive benefits from globalisation which in their view out weighted the negative factors. China has emerged as the largest export market for India. It is also one of the large emerging investors in India. The present ground reality dictates that establishment of normal friendly ties is in the interests of both the countries while they continue their (competitive cooperation) projecting their major roles in the Asia of the 21st century. (Partha Pratim Basu: 9:59).

2. *Befriending Close Neighbours*

India is the recognised pre-eminent power in South Asia. Its close neighbours are Bangladesh, Bhutan, Maldives, Nepal, and Sri Lanka (Pakistan and China have already been discussed) India is the largest country in terms of territory (78 per cent of the region), population (1.2 billion), natural resources, GNP (78 per cent of the region) and military strength. Geographically India is centrally located in the region as it shares 4046 km land border with Bangladesh, 3310 km with Pakistan, 1752 km with Nepal, and 587 km with Bhutan apart from a maritime border with Sri Lanka. (B.C.Upreti: 2006:205). The inter-state relations in the region has been marked by deep rooted turbulence and

hostilities especially involving India and Pakistan which has already been discussed. Even besides Pakistan and India has major or minor border disputes with all its smaller South Asian neighbours except Bhutan. No other country of the region shares border with any other country except India. This Indo centric nature of the region has been a major source of discord. (Sisson and Rose:1990). This unique centrality of India has conferred on the region its common identity and image. It is also noteworthy that India is tied to these countries with bonds of ethnicity, language, religion, culture and other civilisational connections. However in spite of these commonalities India's centrality has spawned a negative image of India in the perceptions of these countries. India has largely been perceived to be a hegemon which is bent on imposing its supremacy on the region and is therefore a threat to their identity and independence. India's relations with these countries have been largely marred by disharmony, suspicion and apathy to a large extent. India has made efforts to counter this Indo-phobia among its smaller neighbours though geo-political and other factors apart from inherent suspicions have prevented these efforts to be converted to amity. (B.C.Upreti: 2008:204).

During the Nehru era India had accorded greater priority to international relations than regional issues. The factors contributing to such an outlook have already been discussed. However as also mentioned the 1990s ushered in a new world order where apart from other considerations the need to accord pre-eminence to regional policy, regional cooperation and regional organisations was keenly felt. Keeping in view this sentiment of the emergence of a new regionalism South Asia too, like other regions of the world, established the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC). Though SAARC was not created to be a platform for solving bilateral problems between India and her neighbours it certainly sought to provide an ambience and mechanism to address regional economic, developmental and ultimately even security issues such as tackling terrorism, drug and human trafficking. and also other problems like climate change, food security and regional connectivity.

While this is not the place to discuss the details of the functioning of SAARC and its successes and failures it may be noted that the organisation has

not quite come up to the expectations generated at the time of its inception in 1985.

India's South Asia policy has recently come under increasing scrutiny due to the fact that the unresolved disputes with some of the smaller neighbours is impacting adversely on its image in the world. While a detailed survey of all the bilateral relations is not in the scope of this paper some specific instances are worth mentioning. India played a major role in the liberation of Bangladesh in 1971. However, its relations with Dhaka have not always been smooth. Sharing of the waters of the common rivers, border disputes and uneven trade relationship are some of the irritants that continue to define the ties between the two countries. New Delhi's relationship with Sri Lanka too has not been free of controversies. The treatment meted out to the Tamil minority on the island nation by successive Sri Lankan governments since its independence from Britain in 1948 has been a source of discord between New Delhi and Colombo. India-Nepal relations have been relatively free from the kind of dissonance witnessed in the cases of Bangladesh and Sri Lanka though there were hitches between the two countries primarily on the issues of trade and transit treaties (Nepal's dependence on India for access to the sea for its trade due to its landlocked status). However, after the abolition of the monarchy in 2008 Nepal has been undergoing a profound and prolonged transition to a popular democracy and India remains naturally concerned that the political process in that country culminates in the establishment of a stable democratic order which would facilitate a more congenial relationship between the two countries.

The challenge that India faces at the moment in its immediate neighbourhood is the establishment of strong and enduring partnerships with the smaller South Asian countries. India needs friendly neighbours not only to concentrate on socio-economic development for itself and the region but also to project a positive image internationally. At the same time New Delhi needs to find a sustainable basis for friendship with its neighbours while retaining political primacy in South Asia which, though, should not be tantamount to the imposition of a hegemonic role in the region. Indeed a stable and prosperous neighbourhood is in India's interest. New Delhi needs to convince its neighbours that India is an opportunity and not a threat.

3. Partnership with Extended Neighbourhood

As has already been mentioned the end of the cold war unleashed hitherto unseen forces in international relations which also offered new opportunities for India's foreign policy. In its desire to establish new partnerships in regions away from South Asia to wield greater influence and clout in international relations in the 21st century New Delhi has begun to pay more attention to South-East Asia and East Asia, Central Asia, the Gulf region and Africa. It all began with the unfolding of India's 'Look East Policy' in the early 1990s. The policy was initiated as a significant step towards developing India's relations with East Asia, South East Asia, Pacific countries as well as the immediate neighbours of India's North East region which had got atrophied during the cold war. According to Lakhan Lal Mehrotra who had served as secretary East in the Ministry of External Affairs this policy is a response to the security threats posed by the Chinese and the great economic potential of the East and South East Asian countries. (Lakhan Lal Mehrotra: 2012). Subsequently India became a full dialogue partner of the Association of South East Asian Nations (ASEAN)-the most successful regional association in Asia-and also a member of the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF). Over the last two decades the policy has evolved from rhetoric to substance as New Delhi's policy makers realised the increasing strategic significance of the region with the world balance of power gradually shifting from the Atlantic to the Pacific. As the South East Asian nations began to register rapid growth in the 1990s India began to feel the need to substantially increase its trade and economic relations with the South East Asian countries. The progress in this direction has been so rapid in recent times that India is now in the process of completing a free trade agreement with the ASEAN.

Since the breakup of the Soviet Union, Central Asia has emerged as a strategically significant region for India. Prior to 1991 most of the Central Asian states were part of the erstwhile USSR and a strategic vacuum was created thereafter which has been sought to be filled by a 'great game' involving the US, Russia and China in almost the 19th century style. The region is rich in its natural resources such as oil and gas; it also provides the shortest transit route to Europe from Asia. With a strong consumer market the region provides tremendous economic prospects in an extended strategic neighbourhood for India in its foreign policy

priorities. Energy rich Central Asia would be particularly important for energy starved India which is expected to be dependent on a huge supply of gas and oil for its rapidly growing economy in the next 25 years. In the coming years New Delhi would be keen to enhance its profile in this region and also combat terrorism, drug trafficking, secure export markets and become an active player in a region neighbouring Afghanistan and Pakistan, the hotbed of Jihadi terrorism. (Rama Sampath Kumar:2010).

The strategic significance of the Persian Gulf region need not be recounted for students of international relations. As is well known it is the primary reservoir of the world's oil and natural gas. Over the past many decades India has imported the bulk of its oil from this region. The region has not featured for much in India's foreign policy considerations except for its dependence on oil imports from this area. The 21st century however offers opportunities to look at the region with a new perspective. As is well known millions of Indian workers are employed in the Gulf and their well being is a constant concern for New Delhi. There are vast opportunities to increase India's trade and industrial links with the countries of the Gulf region. Developing closer economic relationships could benefit millions of people on either side. It has also been suggested that New Delhi can replace bilateralism with multilateralism in its engagements with the countries of the area. Multilateral diplomacy can also bring in countries with whom India has not done business before. In this-regard, India, can follow the example of the ASEAN and seek the status of 'dialogue partner' of the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC). There are opportunities for a pro-active policy in this region. (Kingshuk Chatterjee: 2009:374).

Apart from a brief period during the non-aligned era Africa has largely been neglected by makers of India's foreign policy. However along with the rest of the world Africa is also changing in the post-cold war era and India will have to be sufficiently sensitive, towards these changes. Problems such as mounting debts ,constant deterioration of the terms of trade, bad governance leading to ethnic, religious and other forms of strife and the gigantic scourge of AIDS have made it extremely difficult for most African countries to cope with the challenges of globalisation effectively. In spite of these difficulties India has been quick to recognise the potential of Africa and has already

started new cooperative ventures in the areas of information technology, trade and military ties. There is the potential to collaborate with other developing countries in framing India's Africa policy. India needs to approach Africa with a positive and pro-active set of policies which would be beneficial for both sides. It can identify middle ranging and regionally dominant 'countries such as Egypt, Nigeria and South Africa to expand its network of ties in Africa which would further consolidate. Indo-African ties in the areas of trade, technology transfer and military cooperation on a reciprocal, bilateral and multilateral basis. It may be noted here that China is already present in Africa in a big way and therefore poses challenges for India's Africa policy in the 21st Century. (Hershe: 2009).

4. Extending the Reach of the Defence Forces

In 1962 India fought a disastrous war with China which exposed its lacunae in defence preparedness. Since then the Indian leadership undertook the rapid modernisation of the military on a priority basis. Since it lacked indigenous production capability India turned to foreign suppliers and the Soviet Union emerged as the largest exporter of weapons and weapons technology as the United States would not supply any defence material to India which was not a member of any of the US sponsored alliances and followed a policy of non-alignment. India's nuclear postures also underwent a radical transformation since the Chinese acquisition of nuclear capability in 1964 and the creation of a discriminatory nuclear non-proliferation regime through the Non-Proliferation Treaty of 1970 which allowed the existing nuclear powers-US, USSR, UK, France and China to retain their nuclear arsenal but imposed a prohibition on any further nuclear proliferation. India refused to sign the treaty on the ground of its clearly discriminatory nature and retained its nuclear option which eventually facilitated its path to nuclearisation when it carried out tests in 1974 and 1998. Thereafter India declared itself as a nuclear weapon state, created a command and control system and pronounced a nuclear doctrine which incorporated a 'No first strike strategy'. Acquisition of a nuclear status has conferred on India a deterrent capability vis-a-vis China and Pakistan which are also nuclear powers. However the military modernisation did not remain confined to arming India's defence forces with nuclear weapons. The steady and rapid economic growth over the past two decades has augmented

its capacity to further build its hard power capabilities with military expenditures rising by approximately 350 percent in nominal terms between 1999 and 2009 including purchases of more high end systems. Nominal expenditures rose from roughly \$10.5 billion in 1999 to \$36.6 billion in 2009. (SIPRI Yearbook 2000 and SIPRI Yearbook 2009). As already mentioned India has maintained one of the world's largest armed forces in terms of personnel and in recent years its quality has also improved.

Any state aspiring to a great power status must also possess the capability to project its power beyond its territorial limits. It must think beyond the traditional obsession with territorial defence and be ready to deploy forces beyond the border. Needless to add that India has not reached that stage so far as its land borders are concerned as it is pre-occupied with maintaining its territorial integrity vis-a-vis China and Pakistan. However, in recent years India's maritime capabilities have increased significantly which was not a priority before 1962. The threats that India faced before 1962 were in the landlocked areas of its north and west and emanated from Pakistan and China. Compared to these areas the oceans did not pose any threat to India's defence. However the situation began to change in the 1970s with the beginning of a superpower rivalry in the Indian ocean, growing terrorism and nuclearisation of the oceans. In recent times the increasing activities of the Chinese in the Indian ocean has forced India to give a serious thought to the maritime dimensions of its national security strategy. As the largest littoral state of the Indian ocean India is not only interested in ensuring its security; the ocean's resources are also not less lucrative for a rapidly growing Indian economy.

In recent years the South China Sea has also emerged as an irritant between India and China ever since India agreed to assist Vietnam in the exploration of oil in the region. China considers the South China Sea to be its exclusive preserve and is locked in a dispute regarding its rights in the region with some of its regional neighbours including Vietnam in terms of exploration of the resource rich sea. Beijing considers India to be an interloper in the region and would like New Delhi to stay away. India too does not like Chinese naval activities in the Indian ocean though both the countries have a common interest in keeping the Sea Lanes of Communication (SLOC) in the ocean

free for smooth naval movements from the Persian Gulf to the Straits of Malacca. Nevertheless as long as India and China remain strategic competitors in Asia. Chinese maritime activities in the Indian Ocean, especially in India's maritime neighbourhood, would continue to pose a security threat to New Delhi. (Mukhtar Alam: 2010:85).

5. *Dealing with Major Powers*

As has been mentioned in the first section of this paper the end of the cold war offered opportunities for new directions in India's foreign policy. It also provided the setting for reorienting its relations with the major powers of the world. As non-alignment became increasingly irrelevant in a multi-polar world India also had to make the transition from non-alignment to multi-alignment. In the last two decades India has forged multiple strategic partnerships with the major powers of the world. These include the United States, Russia, the European Union, China and Japan. It needs to be reiterated that as the scope of this paper is limited to an overview it would not be possible to discuss these relationships in detail.

(i) *The United States*

The most dramatic transformation that India's foreign relations have undergone in recent times is with the United States. As is well known the Indo-US bilateral relationship during the cold war was marked by lack of trust, disharmony and even acrimony as the US viewed India's non-aligned stance to be morally wrong in what Washington perceived as an ideological struggle between democracy and communism. The US's initial stand on Kashmir and the subsequent defence relationship with Pakistan, among other things, further contributed to the estrangement between the two countries. The end of the cold war however helped the two countries to view each other in a new light. India now welcomes any kind of US help in stabilising South Asia. Issues which had bedevilled relationship earlier such as Kashmir, nuclearisation and China are less divisive now. The improvement in the relationship found new manifestation in the Indo-US Civil Nuclear Agreement of 2008 which unveiled a range of civil nuclear cooperation between Washington and New Delhi which would have been unthinkable earlier given the track record of India refusing to sign the NPT and the US terminating all kinds of nuclear cooperation with this country and marshalling international efforts to ostracize New Delhi as a nuclear *pariah*. The

deal is too complex to discuss in detail here. However, many analysts have argued that the agreement is virtually an acceptance of India as a defacto nuclear weapon power by America. (S.Paul Kapur:2010:266).

Some of the other select issues that define current indo-US relationship can be highlighted here. Military cooperation, unthinkable during the cold war era, is the most visible aspect of the relationship. The two countries have conducted in recent times a number of joint military exercises both in India and the US. Particular mention may be made of the war games held a few years back when the Indian pilots put up an excellent show which highly impressed their American counterparts. The two countries have also been conducting joint anti-piracy and anti-submarine drills in the Indian Ocean. The US is also interested in Indian combat experiences in high altitude warfare as well as jungle and desert warfare. In an effort to diversify its sources for arms procurement and to reduce its dependence on Russia India has started purchasing American weapons systems. In this regard New Delhi has made it clear that it is not interested in just a buyer-seller relationship but would prefer a more comprehensive relationship that includes the transfer of technology and co-production. Indian purchase of US military equipment is expected to touch \$100 billion by 2022 and \$10 billion would be spent on homeland security (M.J.Vinod:2012:22-23). Another issue that shapes and would continue to shape Indo-US relations this century is their avowed aim to prevent Asia from being dominated by any one power-in other words advancing the cause of Asian stability. Here the China factor plays an important role as Beijing's continued 'rise' as a major political, military, economic and strategic actor in Asia poses a challenge to the traditional role the US has performed on the continent particularly during the cold war era. It may be noted here that the American approach to China and India smacks of a clear ambivalence as, notwithstanding its reservations about China (lack of democracy, its human rights record, the potential rivalry from China in Asia) the US attaches much greater importance to Beijing because of its military and economic clout *vis-a-vis* New Delhi. At the same time there are suspicions in Beijing that Washington is seeking to use New Delhi as a prop against China and its legitimate interests in Asia.

(ii) Other Major Powers

As has been mentioned several-times the desire

for autonomy remains a core Indian priority. Notwithstanding the evolution of its multifarious relationship with the US New Delhi wishes to balance its ties with Washington in seeking leverage through multidirectional partnerships. In this regard Russia, the European union and Japan figure prominently in New Delhi's diplomatic canvas. The disintegration of the Soviet Union had led to a sort of collapse in Indo-Russian relationship as the Russian Federation grappled with the multiple challenges of its transition from communism to market economy and a plural democracy. It is only during the Putin era that Indo-Russian ties have rebounded. A 'Strategic Partnership' was concluded between the two countries in 2000 which resulted, among other things, Moscow emerging again as India's dominant arms supplier swapping obsolete Soviet era hardware for modern equipment. In recent years the two countries concluded a number of pacts for military, technical and economic cooperation. (Ciorciari: 2011:77).

India has also forged what it considers 'Strategic Partnerships' with the European Union and Japan. After some initial indifference towards the EU during its formative years during the 1950s and 1960s New Delhi became alive to the prospects and opportunities the grouping offered after Britain, India's principal link with Western Europe in the aftermath of independence, became a member of the EU in 1973. Since then trade between India and the EU has grown phenomenally and is poised to grow further. The EU today is a political and security dialogue partner of India besides being a major source of developmental, environmental and energy cooperation with New Delhi. (Purusottam Bhattacharya:2012).

During the cold war years India viewed Japan primarily as an American surrogate. However hardly anyone, let alone India, could ignore the remarkable economic resurgence of Japan in the post war era. India's technological and economic cooperation with Japan had started long before the end of the cold war and Japan has traditionally been a major source for aid for India. In the new century the commonalities between the two countries as democracies and stable polities have provided a firm foundation for building a stronger relationship. In the last few years there have been a number of high level visits to and from India and Japan. It should also be noted here that both the countries are locked in disputes with China on territorial issues though this is never mentioned

in public by the leaders of India and Japan in an effort to dispel an impression that they are forging a common front against China.

6. Responding to Challenges of Globalisation Climate Change and Managing Critical Issues

A much talked about phenomenon in the post-cold war phase is the onset of globalisation which 'aims at the establishment of a single global marketplace by integrating national economies through unrestricted flow of commodities, services, labour, capital, technology, information and knowledge.' (K.Ramchandran Nair: 2009:41). It plays a crucial role in the agenda of the Washington Consensus, sponsored by the United States, International Monetary Fund (IMF), the World Bank and the World Trade Organisation (WTO). Many analysts have feared that the present process of globalisation have been geared towards the domination of the rich countries over poorer ones as the agenda was drawn up by the US and its rich allies and supported by the IMF, World Bank and the WTO, Major international developments as far-reaching international treaty obligations regarding trade, investment, taxation, intellectual property rights, banking and financial sector supervision, currency convertibility, foreign policy, the NPT, the CTBT would be imposed on sovereign states. Needless to say that India has been caught in the vortex of these developments and decided to undertake, as has already been mentioned, a policy of liberalisation, privatisation and globalisation (LPG) since 1991. However, it has to ensure that its domestic economic growth, employment, macro-economic stability and inter-personnel equity are not compromised. Another way of countering the adverse effects of globalisation is to mobilise similarly affected and like-minded nations so that a collective stand can be taken by these nations in the global fora to assert their economic and political independence and revive- a strong political will to fight injustices in global relations. (K.Ramchandran Nair:2009:43-45).

However, there are other analysts who argue that globalisation has also opened up immense opportunities for India by linking the Indian economy to the world economy by providing opportunities of vastly enhanced access to the markets, capital and technology of the major economies of the world. Such an exposure would help upgrading skills, standards and technologies enabling weaker economies to become more competitive. It is further argued that these

advantages persuaded India to become a part of globalisation which has helped it to define broadly the areas of concentration of modern development-oriented foreign policy. 'In India's foreign economic policy there is now greater emphasis on attracting more foreign direct investment, including foreign institutional investment; facilitating Indian investment and joint ventures abroad; enhancing earnings from services particularly in the areas of tourism, media, entertainment, healthcare and education; and working in tandem with the private sector in the pursuit of India's economic interests abroad'. (Muchkund Dubey: 2013:14).

Yet another challenge for India's foreign policy in the 21st century is the issue of environmental degradation and climate change. The global climate is changing with more floods and tornadoes in recent times than in the past. The seasons are shifting. There is a discernible upward trend in the average temperature in the last few decades in spite of the fact that recurrent fluctuations in temperature have been observed since records started in 1866. Scientists have taken note of the phenomenon over, the last four decades and international efforts have been underway with the formation of the Inter-governmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in November 1988 in drawing up an action plan for due investigation of the phenomenon and formulation of corrective steps. Most experts are now of the view that the cause is anthropogenic and it is now well known that 'certain gases, named Greenhouse Gases, (GHGs) are responsible for the trapping of the re-radiated heat absorbed by the earth's surface from the sun and the fast increasing concentration of these gases, mainly carbon di-oxide,(CO₂), is of real concern'. (Sujay Basu:2003:229). As is well known most of the environmental issues are interlinked and trans-boundary in nature. Issues like water and flood control and energy cannot only be tackled in a regional framework and along with other problems (ozone depletion, climate change) need global solution. India realises that it needs to work with other developing countries in this regard as its interests are intertwined with theirs. As the industrialised countries have been seeking in international negotiations to impose across the board cuts on emission of GHGs involving both the industrialized and developing countries India has taken a clear and specific stand on the principle of 'Common but differentiated responsibilities' enshrined in the UN framework Convention on Climate Change. India's Environmental Policy states

that the issue cannot be viewed in isolation and must be seen in the context of the developmental needs of the developing countries. India looks at climate change in the context of the promises made by the international community for technology transfer and additional financing which have remained unfulfilled so far, (Ambarish Mukhopadhyay: 2010: 91-98). India has now joined hands with China, South Africa and Brazil to ensure that the industrialised countries which have been primarily responsible for the global environmental problem should bear the burden of capping their emission and the newly industrialising countries such as India, China, South Africa and Brazil should be excluded from this obligation at least for the near future. However there are experts in India who think that in the ultimate analysis these countries which also emit a considerable amount of GHGs (China being the largest emitter) will have to undertake some cuts not only because climate change affects us all but also due to the fact that it is the poorest and the most vulnerable in these countries, including India, who will be the most badly hurt. (Navroz K. Dubash: 2009: 8)

Achieving a great power status is also very much dependent on India's ability to bring about a degree of reforms in international institutions. At the WTO India has been the principal champion in the poor-country cause when it spearheaded opposition to wealthy state's agricultural subsidies during the Doha round as also in resisting the Western trade liberalisation agenda. In spite of facing opprobrium from the first-world capitals India was able to mount a vigorous opposition to Western designs to dominate world trade. India has also been a vocal critic of the IMF and other multilateral banks and their governance. These criticisms yielded results when in October 2010 the G-20 of which India is a member reached agreement on major reforms to the IMF's governing structure which was followed by the IMF announcement in November 2010 that emerging powers were going to get greater weight. India was made the Fund's eighth-largest shareholder. This was a significant step for India which raised the prospect of similar reforms in the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank (ADB). In contrast India's long held aspirations for a permanent seat in the UN Security Council appears to be an uphill task as it is mired in controversies related to the mode and even desirability of the overall reform of the UN. In spite of endorsements of India's candidature by most of the permanent members the situation has

been complicated by the fact that there are other aspirants (Germany, Japan and Brazil) and the opposition from the neighbours of all the four candidate countries. Concern has also been expressed about the efficiency and effectiveness if the Council becomes too large. (Ciorciari: 2011: 77-79).

Looking Forward

India stands today on the threshold of attaining the status of a major power in the not too distant future. As has been mentioned Jawaharlal Nehru had pronounced on the morrow of independence that India deserved to be the fourth power in the world. However, as has been extensively discussed in the voluminous literature on India's foreign policy the regional and the international scenarios during the cold war period did not match up to New Delhi's expectations. While the non-aligned movement did confer on India, at least during its initial years, some influence the defeat in the war with China in 1962 and the emergence of a hostile conflict-ridden scenario involving two of India's most important neighbours-China and Pakistan, turned it into a prisoner of its regional security concerns which considerably diluted its global focus attained through non-alignment earlier. Domestic factors such as developmental challenges, poverty, ethnic, linguistic and religious strife along with the vagaries that a multi party, highly pluralistic democratic society faces have also acted as road blocks in India turning its obvious potential for a major power status into a reality.

As has been discussed in the preceding pages the 21st century however has brought new opportunities. There are positive factors, some of which have already been noted, such as a thriving democracy which continues to attract the admiration of the world notwithstanding its imperfections, a burgeoning economy which, according to many experts, is poised to rank as the third largest in the world by 2050, India's world class IT services which has brought a lot of foreign exchanges as well as laurels for the country in recent years, one of the largest scientific and technological pools in the world, its achievements in outer space explorations which has placed it among the top five nations in this field, a coveted market with a middle class of about 500 million, its soft power which includes its cinema, art and music with a global following and above all its partnership with the United States forged in the post-cold war years, which many experts in India and the Indian

Diaspora believe will stand this country in good stead in this century. However the challenges, including many negative factors, outlined in detail in the preceding pages, are also formidable and have to be confronted successfully if India is to count as a confirmed, accepted and established major power of the world this century. In the last two years India's economic momentum seems to be faltering with GDP growth rates which had been around 8% during much of the last decade slipping to about 5% and the outlook to getting back to the higher growth path in the immediate future does not seem too bright. The partnership with the US can be problematic in the sense that while in bilateral dialogues Washington continues to profess that India would continue to be one of its most important allies doubts remain about India's actual place in American global strategy where China definitely figures much higher than India. India is also worried about the implications about the withdrawal of American and European forces from Afghanistan after 2014 and its fallout for the region. There are also differences of opinion between India and the US on climate change, trade and agriculture. Most importantly India will seek to retain its autonomy and status in the partnership and the US, in the pursuit of its global concerns, may not always be sensitive to India's interests. Most problematic for India's foreign policy this century, as has already been noted, will be its relationship with China and Pakistan which may continue to hamstring its efforts to play a more international role. China remains a difficult actor to deal with, especially on the border issue as recent developments have demonstrated. Repeated Chinese incursions into territories India considers to be its own continue to be a headache for New Delhi. The recently agreed Border Defence Cooperation Agreement (BDCA) during the visit of Prime Minister Manmohan Singh to Beijing "provides a more 'robust protocol' to defuse confrontations and 'build trust' between the rival armies along the 4057 km Line of Actual Control (LAC) till a long term solution of the boundary dispute is worked out." (Sumit Chakravartty: 2013). While the BDCA may not prevent future face-offs between the two armies as there is a serious misperception on both sides as to where the LAC actually lies it "provides a template to manage and defuse face-offs"-and allow the two countries to take appropriate measures according to their own security needs. However notwithstanding the border issue there are positives in Sino-Indian relations which have

already been noted in the section dealing with China. The two countries will simply have to learn to live together within the framework of cooperation and competition.

As already mentioned in the section dealing with Pakistan the challenge of establishing a normal relationship with Islamabad presents New Delhi the most difficult task in the neighbourhood. The election of a new government in Pakistan headed by the Pakistan Muslim League of Nawaz Sharif had raised hopes for better days in bi-lateral relations. However Nawaz Sharif's own commitment, iterated during the election campaign, to improve relations with India have turned out to be a damp squib as, if anything, relations have got worse with Pakistani troops repeatedly violating the cease-fire along the Line of Control (LOC) which had actually started during the regime of the last Pakistani government. Sharif's efforts to again internationalise the Kashmir issue have further irked New Delhi. There appears to be no visible efforts on the part of the new Pakistani government to rein in the Jihadi elements still operating with impunity from the soil of Pakistan. As things stand at the moment and as has been the case for many years India will have to be reconciled with what one observer has termed a 'cold peace' in its relations with Pakistan at least for the near future. (Basu: 2009:62).

Achievement of a major power status for India not only signifies the need to deal with the challenges, discussed in detail in the preceding pages, but also underscores its capability and readiness to shoulder regional and global responsibilities in realms such as energy, environment, terrorism, playing a defining role in international trade and economic relations, promotion of human rights and good governance as well as democracy. As Prime Minister Manmohan Singh has recently pointed out it also means 'developing comprehensive national power' to tackle challenges posed by the shift in the global strategic focus towards the Asia-Pacific region where the US and China jostle for domination. The PM also notes that the economic competition among nations fostered by globalisation has now spread to the security arena. As the economic pendulum is shifting from the west to the east so is the strategic focus. 'This is exemplified by the increasing contestation in the seas to our east and the related 'pivot' or 're-balancing' (of military forces) by the US in the area.' There is uncertainty as to whether these transitions (economic and strategic) will be

peaceful. But the PM reminds the nation that while building its capabilities India has to take into account its limited resource availability. (The Times of India). This reality, along with other impediments discussed earlier, will continue to define India's quest for a major power status in the world in the 21st century.

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